

The systemic dimension of financial numeracy education as a possibility to counter individualistic and neoliberal discourses

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Financial education has been criticized for reproducing neoliberalist and individualistic discourses, often ignoring structural issues related to inequality, power and social justice. Mathematics education can play a role in countering these discourses through what I have come to define as dimensions of financial numeracy education. In this presentation, I report on a project which investigated how financial situations are depicted in mathematics textbooks from Quebec, Canada. I focus on the systemic dimension to argue that mathematics classrooms can address some concerns of individualism and neoliberalism in financial education by presenting financial situations in which sense making is informed by mathematical thinking in connection to other systems of beliefs such as ethics, personal values, beliefs, politics, etc.

Introduction

Financial education has become increasingly important in schools. Despite governments' attempts to tackle successive global economic and financial crises, changes in pension funds, deregulation of housing markets, housing unaffordability, the spread of gig economy practices, and the deepening precarity in work conditions are just some of the challenges faced by individuals and communities in Canada and around the world (Zhang, 2019; McGregor, 2018; Grifoni & Messy, 2012). Most recently, the outbreak of the novel coronavirus and its associated COVID-19 pandemic indicate a severe economic recession potentially worse than what we experienced more than a decade ago.

However, this matter has yet to find mainstream attention in the field of mathematics education. Few researchers have actually developed research programs or lines of inquiry devoted to investigating financial education with a mathematics educational perspective (e.g., Lucey, 2002; Savard, 2008; Hamburg, 2009; Pournara, 2013; Sawatzki, 2014). Their research reveals the uniqueness of dealing with numerical information in financial situations in schools. The implication is that financial education cannot be a mere reproduction of financial knowledge in classroom settings.

Notwithstanding the evident need for students to understand how money circulates in communities and societies, financial education curricula has been heavily criticized. The first critique to financial education (or financial literacy) is that it promotes individualistic

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perceptions of money and personal finances. Critics point out that most curricula around the world strongly emphasize issues of personal finance at the expense of structural inequalities or the role of different actors and institutions in the promotion of well-being. In addition, the content seems to be heavily skewed toward middle class families and their needs: saving for college education, considering payment options, avoiding credit card debt, investing for retirement. Others have also critiqued mathematics education textbooks for constructing an image of middle-class life as the only possibility for happiness and well-being (Manoel, Silva & Valero, 2019; Silva & Valero, 2018).

The second critique is that financial education promotes neoliberalist discourses on the value of education in general, and mathematics in specific. With increasing deregulation of labour conditions, pension plans, health and education, the burden to support oneself and their family has also increased. Much of the arguments for the promotion of financial education acknowledge these realities without promoting critical perspectives (Arthur, 2012). According to critics of financial education, these arguments take economic reforms for granted and do not invite students to question and resist them.

The goal of this paper is to discuss these two critiques within mathematics teaching. In the Canadian province of Quebec, financial education is integrated to secondary mathematics in two ways: 1) as its own strand in grade 11 (when students explore simple and compound interest); 2) as a cross-curricular topic covered in all strands and secondary grades through the *Broad Areas of Learning* (Government of Quebec, n.d.). I have decided to focus on the latter because it represents a longer span of time, more diverse, and yet implicit, content being portrayed to students.

Three dimensions of financial numeracy education

Mathematics has been pointed as an important aspect to successful financial education (Sole, 2014; Lusardi, 2012). However, the mathematics to which I make reference here does not mean its formal or decontextualized representation commonly taught in schools. Instead, I refer to the mathematics that is connected to everyday life. That is what researchers point to as critical to the development of financial education (Sawatzki, 2017; Lucey & Maxwell, 2011). In other words, I use the concept of *financial numeracy* to refer to the knowledge, confidence and ability to use numerical information in financial situations. Within this concept, I draw on the framework of numeracy as social practice (Yasukawa, Jackson, Kane, & Coben, 2018) to conceptualize three dimensions of financial numeracy education: contextual, conceptual and systemic.

The *contextual dimension* refers to the study of mathematics in financial contexts. Consequently, learning about financial concepts and practices is not necessarily part of the goals of the contextual dimension of financial numeracy. Because of that, financial measures (such as price) are only explored as a pretext to learn mathematical concepts (such as decimal numbers or percentages). Furthermore, the teaching of financial numeracy through this dimension tends to be limited to tasks that involve financial contexts. The context itself does not play a major role in justifying solutions of the task.

The *conceptual dimension* refers to the teaching and learning of financial concepts which requires multiple mathematical processes such as: modelling, representing, estimating, measuring, comparing, counting, predicting, rounding, etc. These processes are part of our everyday practices of financial numeracy; hence they reflect the role of mathematics in its development. Many ideas, such as profit, debt and investments, gain deeper layers of complexity once we incorporate the conceptual dimension. Hence, those mathematical processes are necessary to understand financial concepts.

The *systemic dimension* refers to the justification, or unpacking, of financial practices and concepts in relation to other epistemologies. The systemic dimension entails investigating certain financial measures and how they are calculated, defined, modelled and portrayed in society. For that reason, it is situated in pragmatic measurement. While money is used in daily life as a unit to measure goods and services, questioning these measures and unpacking what is behind their establishment is not as common in mathematics curricula. The reasoning behind these measures reveals social, cultural and political actors that use mathematics to convey values. The concept of inflation is a good example: it is common knowledge that inflation is the general increase of prices that happen over time in a given economy, a phenomenon that is real and recognized in our daily lives. However, the calculation of this index is a social and economic convention that requires selecting the basket of goods and services to represent the average increase. The weight with which the items are accounted for in the basket is also a matter of convention. How the final index rate will be used by different institutions, companies and individuals depends on the understanding of this measure as well as the values possessed by each actor. Mathematics plays an important role in empowering individuals to engage in critical debates about how financial concepts are mobilized and measured in daily financial practices, so I incorporate such a role in the systemic dimension of financial numeracy education.

These three dimensions engender a spectrum of financial numeracy. The question that remains to be answered is how these dimensions come together in moments of teaching and learning financial numeracy. In this paper, I focus particularly on the textbooks used by secondary mathematics teachers. I aim to investigate how financial situations are depicted and how those within the systemic dimension can address the issues of individualistic and neoliberalist discourses.

Methodology

I report on my doctoral research which investigated how financial numeracy is depicted in secondary mathematics in Quebec, Canada. The research sought to identify how each dimension of financial numeracy emerged in the textbooks, perceptions and practices of mathematics teachers. In this paper, I discuss the data from the textbooks used in the province's public schools. Three collections of Ministry-approved textbooks were analysed for all secondary grades (grades 7 to 11) with a focus on tasks (exercises, projects, activities, etc.) that incorporated financial situations. These collections covered all 6 grades of secondary school in Quebec, from grades 7 to 11. It is important to notice that in Quebec,

students in grades 10 and 11 are streamed into three mathematics sequences: Culture, Society and Technique (CST); Science (S); and Technique and Science (TS). The CST sequence is typically regarded as the lowest of the three and is targeted to students who aspire careers in the social sciences or trades.

A total of 40 books were analysed. Within these collections, a total of 1362 financial tasks were identified, for an average of 30.3 tasks per secondary grade per collection. Although the majority of tasks were situated within the contextual and conceptual dimensions (which seems to corroborate the notion of mathematics as a neutral space for financial education), 18% of them reflected the systemic dimension of financial numeracy education. The following section presents an overview of what these tasks look like and why they reflect the systemic dimension.

Findings: Systemic dimension in financial tasks

Financial tasks situated within the systemic dimension were often composed of open-ended problems that required students to make sense of their own personal experience in relation to the financial situation being portrayed (e.g., explain why some people go into debt, or justify their purchasing methods). In these tasks, students were being directed to give their personal perspective on the numerical results. Consequently, they could mobilize other forms of reasoning that endorse or challenge the strictly numerical solution. In other words, at the core of the systemic dimension of financial numeracy education lies the possibility of making sense of financial situations through multiple mathematical, cultural and socio-political lenses.

In terms of distribution, the lower grades of secondary school seemed to have a higher incidence of systemic financial tasks. This trend was particularly noticeable among the strands of arithmetic, algebra and, to a lower extent, statistics. The strand of probability, on the other hand, seemed inconclusive given the inconsistency across different collections. Table 1 summarizes the quantitative data collected from the textbooks.

Domain	Unified stream (grades 7, 8, 9)			Streamed curriculum (grades 10, 11)					
	Collection			Collection A			Collection B		
	A	B	C	CST	S	TS	CST	S	TS
Arithmetic	11	14	35				NA		
Algebra	12	11	22	9	5	11	7	4	7
Statistics	8	6	14	5	4	1	1	0	2
Probability	1	0	3	19	NA*	18	2	NA*	6
Geometry	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
TOTAL	34	32	75	33	9	30	10	4	14

* The Quebec curriculum does not allocate any probability content in the SN stream.

Table 1: Summary of financial tasks within the systemic dimension

In the following three subsections, I present a qualitative analysis of the mathematical domains with highest incidence among the textbooks collections (arithmetic, algebra and probability) and discuss how these tasks seemed to incorporate the systemic dimension of financial numeracy education.

Arithmetic

Arithmetic tasks mostly contained multi-step problems that included questions in which the student would provide their own idea (which can be based on mathematics but also on their personal experience). Figure 1, for example, shows a task with the price of gas which posed several questions that aim at understanding how such a financial measure is determined.

La lecture des nombres décimaux

- A Combien coûte un litre d'essence aujourd'hui ?
- B Comment peux-tu répondre à la question précédente sans utiliser le mot « virgule » ou « point » ?
- C Qu'est-ce qui provoque l'augmentation du prix de l'essence ? Demande à tes parents.
- D Que penses-tu de la remarque d'Ariane ?

Translation:

Reading decimal numbers

- a) How much does one litre of gas cost today?
- b) How can you answer the previous question without using a comma or a dot?
- c) What causes the increase of the price of gas? Ask your parents.
- d) What do you think of Ariana's comment?

On the right, Ariana's comment: "My father doesn't care about the increase: he always purchases gas for \$10."

Figure 1: Arithmetic task (Coupal, 2010, p. 56)

Question c asks the students why the price of gas fluctuates. The answer connects to a key feature of the systemic dimension: understanding that a financial measure (price of gas) is established based on a variety of factors. It involves not only costs associated with its production, but also elements such as weather, geopolitics and technical infrastructure. Accordingly, this line of questioning encourages students to engage in critical debates while unpacking these measures. In doing so, students can mobilize different epistemological systems to engage in the problem as opposed to simply carrying a calculation. Also, question d demands that students analyse a statement in which, instead of purchasing the same volume of gas, Ariane's father always purchases \$10. This statement can be analysed in multiple ways that involve mathematical thinking, financial strategies, personal values and sociopolitical stances. Overall, tasks in this category also encouraged students to create their own questions based on rates, proportions and number representations.

Algebra

The systemic dimension emerged in algebra tasks whenever they asked students to give their own idea or make a judgement about a financial situation. They did so through multiple mathematical representations which supported the connection between mathematics and other epistemologies brought up by the students. In Figure 2, for example, different phone plans were presented with graphs in a Cartesian plane.

Figure 2: Algebra task (Boivin, 2009, p. 18)

Each plan was represented by a different function (either linear or stepwise). The question posed to the students was: “if you had a cell phone, which company would you choose?” There is no one single right answer to this kind of question. Instead, students should analyse each phone plan and come up with their own ways of measuring the best choice. This measurement, which is unpredictable, is fundamentally systemic: it will be based on students’ assessments of their own needs, budget, habits, values, sense of fairness, etc. In this case, mathematics acts as a tool that allows them to make sense of their options, but their choice is unavoidably connected to other epistemological systems. In other words, the reasons behind their choice will be informed by multiple epistemologies that might or not include mathematics. This task, then, allows students to work on the systemic dimension financial numeracy education. Other possibilities of questions in this category include giving advice to characters in the task.

Probability

Probability tasks situated within the systemic dimension proposed that students use probabilistic reasoning as an argument to justify financial situations. Figure 3 exemplifies this category in the situation of insurance policies. The task lays out the different prices for life insurance according to the sex of a person and whether they smoke.

Lorsqu'on ne peut pas calculer la probabilité théorique qu'un événement se produise, on a souvent recours aux statistiques pour **estimer** la probabilité de l'événement.

Par exemple, sur sa page web, une compagnie d'assurance met à la disposition du public un calculateur du coût d'une prime d'assurance-vie. Le tableau ci-dessous présente des primes calculées à l'aide de ce calculateur.

**Prime annuelle pour une assurance de 100 000\$
pour une personne née en 1969**

	Fumeurs	Non-fumeurs
Homme	273 \$	154 \$
Femme	207 \$	129 \$

- B** Quels facteurs peuvent influencer le coût de la prime à payer ?
- C** Selon toi, pourquoi y a-t-il une si grande différence entre la prime annuelle pour une femme non fumeuse et un homme fumeur ?
- D** Selon toi, comment procède-t-on pour fixer les primes à payer ?

On peut utiliser la **fréquence** associée à un événement pour estimer la probabilité qu'il se produise.

Figure 3: Probability task (Coupal, 2010, p. 29, our translation below)

Translation:

Since we cannot calculate the theoretical probability of an event, we can resort to statistics to estimate the probability of the event. For example, on its webpage, an insurance company publicizes a calculator for a life insurance premium. The following table presents premiums calculated with the calculator

(in the table: annual premium for a \$100,000 insurance for a person born in 1969, columns: smoker/non-smoker, rows: male/female)

- b) What factors can influence the cost of the premium?
- c) In your opinion, why is there a big difference between the annual premium for a non-smoking female and a smoking male?
- d) In your opinion, how are the premiums established?

We can use the frequency associated with an event to estimate its probability.

Given that prices vary, question b inquires students about what influences the price of an insurance policy. Here, students can use the data provided in the task, but also build on their personal experiences to know that age can impact the price as much as gender, lifestyle, family composition, profession, etc. Furthermore, question c asks about the difference between prices for men and women. Again, justifications can vary, and students can use probabilistic thinking to justify higher prices (men are more likely to die at a younger age) coupled with

a range of other justifications and measures. The systemic dimension is evident here given the opportunity to engage in matters of gender inequalities, corporate policies, public regulation, etc.

Discussion and Conclusion

As it was evidenced by the quantitative data, systemic financial tasks are depicted more frequently in early grades of secondary mathematics in Quebec. In later grades, when students are positioned in streamed sequences, a heavier focus on university entrance is placed onto the curriculum and, consequently, the textbooks. In such cases, mathematics tends to become more abstract and resemble the traditional scholarly discipline. Unsurprisingly, only the CST sequence has introduced financial mathematics into its composition (students who pursue the S and TS sequences tend to explore pre-calculus courses).

Overall, results from the textbook collections show that the systemic dimension of financial numeracy education can be integrated in secondary school in multiples ways with a range of mathematical domains and concepts (particularly arithmetic, algebra, statistics and probability). Mathematics has been identified as a critical component of financial education given that money is essentially a measurement concept (Savard, Cavalcante, Turineck & Javaherpour, 2020). These also show that, if implemented properly, mathematics classrooms can generate perspectives to counter individualistic and neoliberal discourses in financial education.

Individualistic discourses can be addressed in financial tasks through a recognition that different groups and communities do not have access to the same resources (income, credit, confidence, infrastructure, etc.). When students are invited to share their own perspectives to financial situations, there is an opportunity to develop a sense of empathy in mathematics classrooms. They learn that financial situations do not entail one single numerical answer in every case. Mathematics operates then as a medium to communicate these differences, or even as an instrument to unpack and dismantle the myth of meritocracy.

Neoliberal discourses can be addressed in financial tasks when we recognize that economic value should not be the only measure to define our thinking. When students consider the impact of financial situations (portrayed in textbook tasks) to their communities and society, they have the opportunity to unpack the discourses of rational choice when it comes to matters of personal finance. They can also generate knowledge about the roles of government and other institutions in the protection and promotion of financial well-being.

In this paper, I have argued that some of the tasks presented in mathematics textbooks have the potential to construct a more empathetic and critical mathematics classroom environment. However, I also recognize that this is only possible if teachers are sufficiently prepared to identify and tackle sociopolitical matters in mathematics. That includes being aware of what financial education can look like in their classes, hence the importance of incorporating the three dimensions of financial numeracy education in teacher education and professional development. In essence this is about constructing a different epistemology of mathematics education, one in which mathematics is in continuous dialogue with other epistemological systems. The idea that mathematics is a neutral setting for financial

education does more harm than good in countering individualistic and neoliberal discourses, and this is why mathematics educators must be engaged in defining the directions of financial numeracy education.

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